

Yield components and standard heterosis for yield in some F₁ rice hybrids evaluated in Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1984 wet season.

Hybrid	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Growth duration (d)	Disease or insect score ^a		Yield ^b (t/ha)	Standard heterosis to Cisadane (%)
					GM	BLS		
MR365A/BR10	23.4	74.4	22.9	120	0	0	4.8 a	27.65
MR365A/IR36	22.8	74.2	23.0	112	1	1	4.6 a	22.87
MR365A/IR52	23.2	73.1	24.0	109	1	1	4.3 b	14.63
MR365A/IR54	23.8	64.2	23.6	116	1	1	3.5 d	-7.44
MR365A/IR60	22.0	61.4	19.8	130	1	1	3.5 d	-7.97
MR365A/IR46	21.7	79.5	23.0	132	1	5	3.4 de	-9.04
MR365A/IR26	23.5	77.7	23.5	134	1	1	3.2 e	-16.22
MR365A/IR50	22.6	62.4	21.0	120	1	1	3.2 e	-15.69
Cisadane ^c	23.7	81.9	28.9	142	1	1	3.8 c	-
IR36	22.9	83.9	20.7	120	3	3	3.6 cd	-

^a Scoring based on 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. GM = gall midge, BLS = bacterial leaf streak. ^b Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

^c Best check variety.

Indonesian conditions, MR365A could be used in developing F₁ rice hybrids using IR36, JR52, and BR10 as restorer lines. However, the CMS line is not stable for pollen sterility. □

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Identification of restorers and maintainers for four CMS lines of rice

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We crossed 17 cultivars of early, medium, and late duration (as male parents) with 4 cytoplasmic genetic male sterile lines (IR46830A, IR46831A, Zhen Shan 97A, and V20A) to identify their fertility restorers and maintainers.

The F₁ seeds were germinated in petri dishes, transferred to pots, and transplanted in the field 30 d after germination.

Varieties were classified on the basis of spikelet fertility in their F₁ hybrids: restorers = >80% spikelet fertility, partial restorers = 10-79%, and

Fertility restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for 4 CMS lines. Pantnagar, India.

CMS line	Fertility restorer	Partial restorer	Maintainer
IR46830A	Narendra 1 Saket Basmati 370	IET7613 Narendra 2 Mahsuri Govind IR58 Manhar UPR82-42 Pant Dhan 6	Ratna N22 Rasi
IR46831A	-	Manhar Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Govind	Pant Dhan 4
Zhen Shan 97A	-	Saket 4	-
V20A	-	Pant Dhan 4	-

maintainers = <10%.

Narendra 1, Saket 4, and Basmati 370 were effective restorers for IR46830A. Ratna, N22, and Rasi were identified as maintainers for this CMS line (see table). Pant Dhan 4 was a maintainer

for the CMS line IR46831A.

No fertility restorer was identified for Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, and IR46831A. There was segregation for fertility in the F₁ when V20A was crossed with Pant Dhan 4. □

Media conditioning to convert nonembryogenic rice calli to embryogenic calli

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We investigated the effect of media conditioning on converting rice

nonembryogenic (NE) callus to embryogenic (E) callus.

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. S201) seeds were dehulled mechanically, surface sterilized in 5% sodium hypochloride solution for 30 min, and rinsed 3 times with sterile distilled water. Seeds were sown in basal salts and vitamins of Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with 200 mg myo-inositol/liter, 100 mg thiamine HCl/liter, 3% (wt/vol) sucrose, and

0.7% Difco Bacto agar (pH 5.7). Cultures were incubated under complete darkness at 22 ± 2°C.

Ten-day-old seedlings were cut in 2- to 3-mm pieces and cultured in a callus formation medium consisting of germination medium supplemented with 20 μM 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). Five petri dishes each containing pieces of four seedlings were used per treatment. All cultures were subcultured every 4 wk.